

OVERVIEW ABOUT THE MOST IMPORTANT THEORIES/MODELS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract

Purpose – the aim of this paper is to present the specific elements of the most important theories/models of economic growth.

Methodology/approach - the data sources used in the study are numerous: papers, books etc. This information has been analyzed and interpreted by the authors.

Findings – the study shows that the models of economic growth have been developed according to the economic realities of the period in which they have been advanced.

Research limitations/implications – the limitations of this study refer to the fact that we did not use an exhaustive approach and we considered only a limited number of theories of economic growth.

Practical implications – the practical implications of this study derive from our conclusions, and it refer to the fact that a model of economic growth, in order to be viable, it should take into account the economic realities of the analyzed period.

Originality/value – the originality of this study is reflected by the fact that we employ a comparative approach on the most important models of economic growth, from their characteristics' point of view and not from the point of view of the mathematical models used to develop those theories.

Key words: economic growth, growth models.

Introduction

Economic growth has been, and it continues to be, a very important topic in the literature and a highly debated one. This is, mainly, due to the benefits of it on society, in general, and on individuals, in particular. The economists that have studied the process of economic growth formation, have considered the identification of factors that positively or negatively affect this process. Each model of economic growth that has been developed over time has identified one or more determinants of economic growth, either endogenous or exogenous, considering the economic realities of the period in which the model has been developed and the economic thought that characterized their proponents.

The most important theories/models of economic growth

During the time have been proposed many theories that try to explain the economic growth process. From the point of view of the moment in time they have been advanced, these theories may be classified in four main categories: Classical theories, Keynesian theories, neoclassical theories and modern theories.

In the category of classical theories of economic growth are included, especially, the theories developed by Adam Smith, Thomas Malthus and David Ricardo. The first ideas that contain aspects regarding economic growth have appeared in the mercantilist period, between mid XV-th century and mid XVIII-th century, before the apparition of the classical school of economic thought (end of XVIII-th century). As stated by McDermott (1999), mercantilist theory advanced the idea that the welfare of a nation resides in its economic power and that the accumulation of wealth represents the main source of economic growth. In a chronological order, other ideas regarding economic growth have been also formulated by some representatives of physiocracy, a current of economic thought that precedes mercantilism. The most representative exponent of this current of economic thought is considered to be François Quesnay. As stated by Muller (1978), during the period in which F. Quesnay lived (18th century), the level of economic development of a country was determined almost entirely by the level of output achieved in agriculture. Starting from the reality of those times, Quesnay considers that obtaining a production surplus in agriculture and reinvesting it in the following year to obtain a higher production represents a way to ensure economic development.

Adam Smith is considered both the father of classicism and liberalism, he is the one who postulated the "laissez-faire" principle in economic theory. In his most famous work "Wealth of Nations", written in 1776 during the industrial revolution, A. Smith tries to identify and analyze the factors that contribute to the growth of the wealth of nations. If the physiocrats considered that nature (land) is, if not the only, than the main factor of production and that economic development derives from agriculture, A. Smith emphasizes the determining role of industry in obtaining economic growth based on the efficient use of three factors of production: nature, work, and capital (considered as inputs). To obtain the highest possible output (that will further take to an increase in economic growth) it is necessary to increase the inputs. The first factor of production (nature/land) being finite, it follows that we must act on the growth of the other factors of production, namely labor and capital. In fundamenting his theory, Adam Smith started from the hypothesis that profit should be reinvested in increasing production, thus avoiding accumulation. Thus, according to Adam Smith, economic growth is based, in particular, on the growth of capital and on the division of labor (specialization). As stated by Ucak, A. (2015), Adam Smith also considered technical progress and ensuring an appropriate economic framework in which the invisible hand of the market can make its mark as important determinants in achieving economic growth.

Thomas Malthus remained in the history of economic thought, mainly, due to the principle of population formulated in his famous work entitled "An Essay on the Principle of Population", which essentially postulates the fact that population growth, if not controlled, will exceed our ability to produce enough food for the entire population, thus generating hunger and poverty. As stated by Unat (2020), Malthus's pessimistic vision was based on the limited character of the land available for agriculture, which cannot provide sufficient agricultural production to cover the entire demand. Thomas Malthus argued that there was an inconsistency between the population growth rate (which increases in geometric progression) and the growth rate of agricultural production (which only increases in arithmetic progression). In other words, the population growth rate is higher than the economic growth rate and measures must be taken to decrease the population growth rate and to reduce poverty.

David Ricardo tried and succeeded in taking the economic ideas of Adam Smith and Thomas Malthus to a higher level, transforming and integrating them into a true theory of economic growth that he presented in his reference work entitled "Principles of political economy and taxation". As stated by Narasimhuiu (1977), for D. Ricardo economic growth is a null variable and the active variable is the distribution of income (determining the way in which profits are distributed is a challenge to which economic theory and practice must respond as precisely as possible). The premise from which D. Ricardo started was that in agriculture, profitability is decreasing, while in industry profitability is considered to be constant. In D. Ricardo's view, economic growth depends on the accumulation of capital and this depends on the reinvestment of the profits obtained both in agriculture and in industry. In agriculture, the accumulation of capital depends both on the productivity of the agricultural land and on the technical level of the machines used.

John Maynard Keynes was not only a famous economist, but also the one who created an important school of economic thought: Keynesism. Unlike most classics, Keynes was in favour of state intervention in the economy to ensure/restore economic balance, especially in times of crisis. Keynes claims that if the saved part of the global income were equal to the investments, economic equilibrium could be reached. However, in the real economy, not everything that is saved or accumulated is invested, which explains the presence of imbalances in the economy. Alone (without the intervention of the state), the free market fails to create the favorable conditions to ensure an economic growth that leads to the well-being of the population.

Roy Harrod and Evsey Domar are not only two followers of the Keynesian theory, but also outstanding personalities who contributed to the development of the theory of economic growth. They remained in the history of economic thinking as developers of a model that bears their name (the Harrod-Domar model), even if the efforts made by the two to develop the theory of economic growth were independent. This model tries to transform Keynes' model, presented in the work "The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money", which took into account a short time horizon, into a model that is valid over a longer time horizon, starting from the assumption that savings are the source of investments. The Harrod-Domar model, which is part of the category of so-called exogenous growth models, postulates the fact that the economic growth rate depends, directly proportionally, on two important factors: the saving rate in the economy and the productivity level of the capital.

The Harrod Model considers 3 categories of rates: the warranted growth rate, the actual growth rate, and the natural growth rate. The guaranteed rate ensures the expected profit to the investors, the real rate is the one resulting from the accounting calculations and the natural rate is the one that assumes the full use of all the other production factors. Among the three rates, the guaranteed one is considered by R. Harrod to be the main determinant of balance and economic growth.

Neoclassical theories of economic development were developed, in particular, by Trevor Swan and Robert Solow. The exogenous economic growth model proposed by the two economists, known as the Solow-Swan model, is a development of the Harrod-Domar model. As stated by Moroianu, N., and D. Moroianu (2012), the particularity of this model is that it accounts for a new element: the productivity growth. In this model, which starts from the assumption of a perfectly competitive economy, new capital is more valuable than old capital due to the improvement of technology over time. The conclusion reached by R. Solow and T. Swan is that in the absence of technological development, the economy goes towards a steady state, therefore long-term economic growth is determined by technical progress. Thus, the difference between rich and poor countries is due to existing differences at the level of technology (a higher rate of technical progress in developed countries compared to other countries). In opposition to R. Harrod and E. Domar, R. Solow believes that the savings rate has no influence on long-term economic growth, but only on the income level. Regardless of the level of savings

and implicitly of investments, sooner or later, the process of economic growth reaches the "steady state" stationary stage.

Another neoclassical model of economic growth, known as the Cass-Koopmans-Ramsey model, combines the contribution of Franck P. Ramsey, David Cass and Tjalling C. Koopmans to the development of economic growth theory. This model is a modified form of the Solow-Swan model, which starts from the premise that the saving rate is endogenous, optimally chosen by households, unlike the Solow-Swan model which considers that the saving rate is an exogenous and constant variable. The Cass-Koopmans-Ramsey model considers that there are two categories of agents acting on the market: firms and households, each of them trying to optimize their profit, respectively utility. The model analyzes the performance of the economy considering the rational behavior of individuals who seek to maximize their utility. According to this model, in the long run, the economy tends toward a state of equilibrium in which capital, production, consumption, and investment grow at the same rate as the actual labor force.

The modern/new models of economic growth appeared as a reaction to the limitations of neoclassical models that determine the rate of economic growth only based on exogenous variables. Starting with the 60s and especially with the 80s of the last century, several specialist works appeared in which economic growth is explained taking into account endogenous economic variables: Kenneth Arrow (1962), Robert Lucas (1988), Paul Romer (1990), Gene Grossman (1991), Elhanan Helpman (1991), Philippe Aghion (1992), Peter Howitt (1992), etc.

For example, Kenneth J. Arrow proposed in 1962 the "learning by doing" model, which considers that the development of human resources is carried out continuously, through learning, the accumulation of knowledge contributing to continuous economic growth. Robert Lucas also talks about the role of human resources in economic growth, who believes that the greater the time devoted to learning outside the program hours, the greater will be the productivity of work, and therefore the economic growth.

As stated by Jones, C.I. (2019), perhaps the most well-known model that is part of the category of modern/new theories of economic growth is the one proposed by P. Romer in 1990. An important premise from which P. Romer started in designing his model was the one that companies use ideas and different categories of goods in practice. Unlike goods which are rivals, ideas are non-rivals. These ideas can be the basis of economic growth. For P. Romer, the role of human resources is decisive in the research-development sector, a sector that must contribute to the production of new capital goods. Thus, Romer provides a theory of endogenous technological change that highlights the important role of researchers and entrepreneurs.

In 1991, Gene Grossman and Elhanan Helpman proposed a growth model based on the process of innovation and imitation. Innovation is related to the activity of creating new products, while through imitation the new knowledge follows a process of diffusion, from the more technologically developed regions to the less developed ones (Grossman, G.M and E. Helpman, 1994). Innovation and imitation are, in the opinion of the two economists, the engine of technological progress. Unlike P. Romer who considered that the introduction of new capital goods constitutes the basis of economic development, G. Grossman and E. Helpman believe that development can be achieved by diversifying consumer goods.

Discussion and conclusions

The current paper aims to make a retrospective of the most representative theories of economic growth developed over time. We have to make a remark from the beginning: there is no best theoretical model of economic growth. Each individual theory tries to explain an economic reality according to the period in which they were proposed. If the mercantile and,

partially, the classic models tried to express an economic reality in which agriculture had a major role, with the industrial revolution and the development of the industrial sector, the economic picture changed and, implicitly, new determinants of economic growth were identified. In the following table, we tried to present the main determinants of economic growth identified by the most representative authors of economic growth theories:

Table 1. The main determinants of economic growth

Author/authors	The main determinants of economic growth
Adam Smith	- capital increase; - division of labor (specialization); - technical progress;
Thomas Malthus	- the population growth rate.
David Ricardo	- capital accumulation; - reinvestment of profits;
Roy Harrod and Evsey Domar	- the saving rate in the economy; - the productivity level of the capital;
Trevor Swan and Robert Solow	- technical progress (the rate of exogenous technical change).
Franck P. Ramsey, David Cass and Tjalling C. Koopmans	- the rate of exogenous technical change;
P. Romer	- innovation and R&D activities; - the introduction of new capital goods;
Gene Grossman și Elhanan Helpman	- innovation and imitation; - diversification of consumer goods;

A major difference between economic growth theories refers to the way in which they try to explain the phenomenon of economic growth: by means of exogenous or endogenous variables. Models proposed by Roy Harrod, Evsey Domar, Trevor Swan, Robert Solow are considered to be exogenous models, in which the growth rate is calculated based on some exogenous variables. The more recent endogenous growth models, proposed, among others, by Kenneth Arrow, Robert Lucas, Paul Romer, Gene Grossman, Elhanan Helpman, etc., try to explain the phenomenon of economic growth based on the internal conditions existing at the company level.

Unlike the classical and neoclassical models, the modern models of economic growth consider as many aspects of the contemporary economic reality as possible: imperfect competition, national and international economic interdependencies, etc. which gives them a greater dose of reliability. The transition from purely theoretical models, based on simplifying assumptions in which, for example, competition was considered perfect, to modern models that are better reflecting the real economy was not achieved overnight, but required the work of many well-known economists who took over and developed the work of their predecessors in the field of economic growth theory.

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